

Speculation on the Stationary Classical Action and Quantum Free Particle

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We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativity and is dependent on both the deterministic $x=vt$ and fluctuation/probabilistic $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. In other words, both determinism and probability are inherent to special relativity and it is also special relativity which defines energy and momentum. At first, it may seem that these are rather strong suggestions.

We argue, however, that perhaps these ideas are already present in classical Lagrangian/Stationary Action theory. This theory was developed to describe Newtonian mechanics, but we argue that because it uses the notions of E (energy) and p (momentum), it must be linked to special relativity which yields the full expressions for these functions. The interesting feature of stationary Lagrangian theory is that a notion of fluctuations in path (x, v, t) are used to ultimately obtain the deterministic path $x=vt$ for a free particle as the stationary one. The notion of a stationary, deterministic path $x=vt$ is present, but so is the notion of fluctuations about this path. The problem is that the stationary action process is a mathematical one and does not attribute and physical features to the fluctuations about the stationary path, whereas we argue that these fluctuations are linked with probabilistic impulse hits or E interactions in time and are directly associated with the quantum wavefunction (complex probability) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which physically manifests itself (as in 2-slit experiments etc).

In order to connect stationary classical action theory to special relativity, we use $H = pv - L \rightarrow -\hbar dt + p dx = L dt$. If one considers fluctuations of this equation, the RHS set to 0 leads to the stationary deterministic $x=vt$, while the LHS leads to $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. In other words, there is a Δx and Δt not linked to $v = \Delta x / \Delta t$. We suggest that this approach shows both probabilistic and deterministic features present side by side and is directly linked to special relativity because $-\hbar dt + p dx$ is of the form of the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.

The Notion of Determinism and Fluctuations

Newtonian mechanics is a deterministic theory. Later, stationary classical action theory was introduced:

$$\Delta \int L(x,v,t) dt = 0 \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{where } L(x,v,t) \text{ usually} = \text{kinetic energy} - V(x) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{leads to the differential equation } \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dL}{dv} - \frac{dV}{dx} = 0 \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{For a free particle, one has: } \frac{d}{dt} v = 0 \text{ or } x=vt \text{ for } x\text{-initial} = 0 \text{ and } t\text{-initial} \quad ((4))$$

Interestingly, Δ in ((1)) considers paths with the same start and endpoints, but different x , v and t values, i.e. special fluctuations. These, however, are math fluctuations as the entire

process of ((1)) is a math approach. The fluctuations are not considered as being physical and so are examined further in stationary action theory.

We also note that this theory contains the equation:

$$H = pv - L \quad \text{where } p = dL/dv \text{ partial and } H = \text{energy in many cases} \quad ((5))$$

It is ((5)), which suggests examining its link with special relativity.

Special Relativity

Special relativity which defines fully E and p. We argue that stationary action theory cannot be considered independently of special relativity because there is no a priori notion of E and p (except in the Newtonian approximation $v \ll c$).

In previous notes, we have argued that special relativity is built from the deterministic equation $x=vt$, because moving frames are involved and one needs an equation to describe constant speed motion. We proceeded further, however, by arguing that the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((6))$$

, which is ultimately based on the deterministic $x=vt$, allows for fluctuations

$$x + \hbar/p, \quad t + \hbar/E \quad ((7))$$

which leave ((6)) unchanged. These fluctuations may be used to keep E and p independent because they are very different kinds of interaction variables. We further argued that this independence may be used to create a probability which allows for independent conservation of E and p:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((8))$$

One might, however, argue that introducing the fluctuations ((7)) is over-reaching, especially since one associates with them probabilistic impulse p hits in x (and E in t). One considers a probabilistic-deterministic hybrid model, with $x=vt$ being the deterministic part and ((8)), the probabilistic. We suggest, however, that some of these ideas may already be present in classical stationary action theory.

The Link Between Special Relativity and Stationary Action Theory

The usual interpretation of special relativity is deterministic. One does not traditionally introduce ((7)) to the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$. On the other hand, the notion of fluctuations (i.e. paths other than $x=vt$ for a free particle) is at the core of the stationary action theory. It is this

same action theory which uses E and p and so must somehow be linked to special relativity because it is the latter which defines E and p.

If one examines ((5)), one may write:

$$-H dt + p dx = L dt \quad ((9))$$

One may consider an integral of both sides of ((6)), but the stationary approach is within the integral (even though integration by parts is used for $\delta x/\delta t$). One takes δ of both sides of ((6)). On the RHS, setting this to 0 leads to determinism, i.e.

$$d/dt dL/dv \text{ partial} = 0 \text{ for a free particle with } L = .5mv^2 \text{ in the nonrelativistic case and } -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \text{ in the relativistic } \quad ((10))$$

δ on the LHS which is set to 0, cannot, however, lead to δx and δt being linked with v . Rather, these must be linked with fluctuations from the deterministic result. To obtain 0 on the LHS, one employs ((7)). The fundamental question is whether one may attribute any physicality to δx and δt . We argue that one should be able to as one is not using any type of a priori math procedure such as extremization (used in the stationary action case). The RHS yields determinism, while the LHS side yields probabilistic interactions (i.e impulse hits in space). Thus, we argue that the notion of obtaining free particle quantum mechanics from special relativity is consistent with some of the ideas of classical stationary action theory, but add the idea that fluctuations have physical meaning, i.e. there is an actual physical probability in space linked with impulse hits, which is borne out by the 2-slit experiment.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have often argued that free particle physics arises from special relativity, in particular the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ because one may have x,t or $x+h\bar{p}/p$, $t+h\bar{E}/E$ yield the same invariant value. We suggested that this implies a probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ associated with interactions which conserves E and p independently. At the same time, one has determinism through $x=vt$.

Here we argue that some of these ideas may possibly appear in Lagrangian theory/ stationary action theory. This theory makes use of E and p (and so must be linked to special relativity which defines these quantities) and at the same time uses the notion of fluctuations to obtain the deterministic $x=vt$. We argue that $H= pv - L$ may be transformed into $-Hdt + p dx = Ldt$. If one takes δ of both sides, the RHS yields the usual Lagrangian differential equation whose solution is the deterministic $x=vt$ if the RHS is set to 0, while setting the LHS to zero yields ((7)) which introduces probability. Here one may see determinism arising on one side of an equation and probability on the other showing how the two work hand-in-hand in free particle quantum mechanics, we argue.

References

1. Quantum Wavefunction and Fluctuation of Classical Action